

HP sintering of yttrium-aluminate glass microspheres

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ABSTRACT

Rare earth aluminate-based materials with eutectic microstructures represent an interesting approach to ceramics with important mechanical properties (hardness, fracture strength /toughness), thermal stability and creep resistance at elevated temperatures. These properties are attributed to strong eutectic interfaces between present phases and designate these materials for various aerospace (jet aircraft engines) and industrial (high efficiency power generation gas turbines components) applications. The combination of precipitation method and flame synthesis was used for preparation of glass microspheres with eutectic composition in system $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3$ in our previous work [1]. The prepared microspheres were HP (hot press) sintered at different temperatures and different holding times. IR transparent ceramics and glass ceramics with fine two phase microstructure with Al_2O_3 and YAG phases percolating at submicrometre level and with hardness exceeding 15 GPa resulted from the experiments. In this work, the yttrium-aluminate glass microspheres with eutectic compositions were prepared by combination of sol-gel Pechini [2] method and flame synthesis to achieve a better compositional homogeneity of glass microspheres and improved mechanical properties of final bulk ceramic materials. The prepared glass microspheres were hot-press sintered at different conditions. The hardness and fracture toughness of prepared ceramics materials was measured and final microstructures were studied by SEM analysis (Fig.1). From comparison of results is clear, that higher pressure and holding time 30 min increasing of mechanical properties in samples sintered at temperatures ≥ 1300 °C. The highest values of hardness 18.0 ± 0.7 GPa and of fracture toughness 4.9 ± 0.3 $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ was obtained in sample sintered at 1600 °C, pressure 80 MPa and with holding time 30 min. Similarly, higher values of hardness 16.3 ± 0.8 GPa, fracture toughness 5.5 ± 0.8 $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ were obtain in sample sintered at 1600 °C, pressure 30 MPa for 30 min. Also in both cases the coarsening of the microstructure was observed by SEM analysis and presence YAG and $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ crystalline phases in samples was confirmed by XRD analysis. These results indicates, that sintering of samples at higher temperatures and for longer time causes the growth of $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ grains and formation of YAG/ Al_2O_3 microstructure, where YAG grains are reinforced by well-connected $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ matrix.

Fig.1 SEM micrographs of samples sintered at 1050°C, 80 MPa for 30 min (a), at 1600°C, 30MPa for 30 min (b) and at 1600°C, 80 MPa for 30 min (c)

Possibility of preparation of ceramic materials with fine-grained (submicron) microstructure and interesting mechanical properties by hot-press sintering of glass microspheres was confirmed.

Keywords: SEM, Vickers hardness, yttrium-aluminate glasses

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References:

- [1] A. Prnová, D. Galusek, M. Hnatko, J. Kozánková, I. Vávra, Composites with eutectic microstructure by hot pressing of Al_2O_3 - Y_2O_3 glass microspheres, *Ceramics – Silikáty*, 55 (2011) 208-213
- [2] M.P: Pechini, Method of preparing lead and alkaline-earth titanates and niobates and coating method using the same to form a capacitor, U. S. Pat. No. 3 330 697, July 11 (1967)